

Business Development Using Business Model Canvas to Increase Competitiveness in Anata Burger Business

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to develop the Anata Burger business by implementing the Business Model Canvas (BMC) to improve competitiveness. The analysis was conducted on nine elements of the BMC through observation, interviews, and sales data. The results show an improvement in product quality and sales of up to 23.21% after implementing modern packaging changes and expanding digital channels such as GoFood and QRIS digital payments. Customers provide positive feedback, but improvements in human resource management and digital marketing are needed for sustainable business growth. This research offers practical guidelines for the management of Burger Anata to refine their business model and market strategy, as well as serving as a reference for other SMEs in adopting innovation and digitalization to enhance competitiveness.

KEYWORDS: Business Model Canvas, Business Development, Competitiveness, MSMEs.

A. INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are one of the contributions of MSMEs to the nation. Besides boosting the country's economic growth, MSMEs play a significant role in absorbing labor in the informal sector and distributing income, especially in rural areas (Akbar et al., 2024; Nursini, 2020). Business development is a key factor underlying business success to maintain productivity, including prioritizing the implementation of well-formulated business strategies combined with continuous innovation to make products more competitive and support business success (Lestari et al., 2024). This relates to the current conditions, which play an important role in Indonesia's economic contribution (Surya et al., 2021).

Efforts to develop businesses can be carried out by applying business model strategies such as the Business Model Canvas (BMC) to improve organizational and business management. Furthermore, this model illustrates how companies can create added value in their products. The Business Model Canvas has nine important factors that help understand future business models. These factors are considered to simplify business focus on critical points and reduce risks, making this vital tool capable of creating an effective and efficient MSME business. The nine factors are essential in helping to understand business models in the future (Osterwalder et al., 2019).

This study, conducted on Burger Anata, aims to identify how business development using the Business Model Canvas approach can help the company achieve competitive advantage in the market. Burger Anata is one of the fast-food MSMEs that has been operating and wants to continue growing amid increasing competition. Business development with the Business Model Canvas approach can assist Burger Anata in competing more effectively and achieving competitive advantage (Rahmi, Rakib et al., 2024).

Burger Anata is an MSME in Makassar, South Sulawesi, engaged in the fast-food sector. Founded in 2024, the business aims to meet market demand for quality burgers using fresh ingredients and innovative flavors. From the beginning, Burger Anata has focused on delicious products that appeal to consumers concerned with food quality. As a micro, small, and medium culinary business, Burger Anata faces challenges due to many competitors in the same business sector, with numerous new culinary MSMEs emerging. To survive, Burger Anata creates products by adding menu options. The business owner wants to expand market reach but still uses a conventional approach by selling directly at the outlet (Akin, 2024). However, Burger Anata faces various challenges in its business development. Key barriers include a less strategic location, ineffective marketing strategies, and limited human resources as operations are still managed by the owner and some relatives. Additionally, production is done manually on a small scale, adjusted to orders to avoid accumulating perishable materials, limiting production capacity and profit. (Ellitan, 2019).

Objective

In this study, it will be analyzed how product innovation influences repurchase intention through customer satisfaction. This research is important to be conducted in Makassar City because Makassar City in the catering service business has quite tight competition, so that later this research can help.

B. LITERATUR REVIEW

1. Business Model Canvas (BMC) Business Development

Business development emphasizes increasing knowledge for future work performance. This involves an integrated approach with other activities to change work behavior (Li et al., 2019). However, Anoraga and Wijaya's perspective is broader, encompassing motivation, creativity, and foresight as essential components of business development. Therefore, according to Anoraga and Wijaya, effective business development involves entrepreneurial responsibility, foresight, motivation, creativity, and overall performance improvement.

According to (Malik, 2020), business development is the responsibility of every entrepreneur and requires foresight, motivation, and creativity. If entrepreneurs can achieve these, there is a significant opportunity to grow small businesses into medium-sized and even large-scale enterprises.

a. Customer Segments

Customer Segments refers to determining the target customers of Burger Anata, such as teenagers, college students, young families, or office workers around the business location. Customers who use the services/products of the organization can also be segmented based on behavior, age, profession, income, and geography. The customer segment reflects the market share reached by Burger Anata, which includes all groups, from teenagers to adults. Specifically, this segment includes students, housewives, and the general community. Burger Anata's customer segment is a mass market, covering all groups.

b. Value Propositions

Burger Anata delivers value to its customers by providing quality services, which is also an added value offered, as Burger Anata pays great attention to service quality to attract customers. Aspects such as cleanliness, safety, comfort, neatness, timeliness, and employee politeness must always be maintained and improved.

c. Channel

Channel is an element such as communication, distribution, and sales channels that describe how the organization communicates with its customer segments and delivers its value proposition.

d. Customer Relationship

Burger Anata's relationship with its customers falls under personal assistance, where communication is conducted directly. It involves monitoring operations and routinely ensuring customer satisfaction by asking customers about complaints and their experiences.

e. Revenue Streams

Revenue Streams represent the incoming funds that describe how the organization earns income in the form of money from each customer segment. The revenue stream received by Burger Anata comes from its sales as a burger stall.

f. Key Resources

Key Resources describe the most important assets that determine the success of operating the business model, such as buildings, vehicles, intellectual property, and labor. Burger Anata's key resources consist of human resources (HR) and operational equipment.

g. Key Activities

Key Activities are the main activities that support the success of a business model in delivering its value propositions to customers. The key activities performed by Burger Anata include operational services such as preparing food according to customer needs (selling burgers and side dishes).

h. Key Partnership

Key Partnership is a voluntary business cooperation agreement between two or more companies to complete a specific project. This cooperation can lead to cost savings, risk reduction, and obtaining resources not owned by the company.

i. Cost Structure

Cost Structure describes all costs incurred as a result of operating this business model to realize value propositions through channels and key resources. The cost structure incurred by Burger Anata includes costs for human resources and operational expenses.

2. Competitiveness

Discussion about company competitiveness has long been a popular topic, with many definitions related to this concept. Some experts mention that competitiveness is a function of identifying the right market product dimensions for the company's positioning. Competitiveness can be achieved through economies of scale, improving management capabilities, and technological capacity (Lestari et al., 2024; Handoyo et al., 2023). The results of research on MSMEs in Makassar City show that competitive advantage significantly strengthens the existence of MSMEs, with business innovation and digital literacy as the main supporting factors in creating sustainable competitiveness (Rakib et al., 2024).

In various theories about competitiveness, it is concluded that the success or failure of an organization heavily depends on its ability to adapt to changes in the surrounding environment. Management literature also emphasizes that companies often face various environmental challenges that can actually become opportunities, not just threats. The business environment needs to be faced and reinterpreted to support strategy development. This shows that a company's ability to adapt to business environment conditions is a key factor in determining success. The better a business actor adapts to its business environment, the greater their potential to achieve competitive advantage (Putera et al., 2021).

C. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative approach with a development research type. This approach emphasizes understanding social phenomena from the participants' perspectives, namely individuals who are interviewed, observed, and asked to provide data, opinions, ideas, and perceptions. Data collection techniques include in-depth interviews, observation, and documentation, aiming to gain a deep understanding of social phenomena based on participants' experiences and views. The research focus is the business development of Burger Anata using the Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach, which includes nine main elements: customer segments, value propositions, distribution channels, customer relationships, key activities, key resources, key partnerships, revenue streams, and cost structure. The research object is Burger Anata, a culinary business located at Jl. Landak Baru No. 82, Rappocini District, Makassar City. The research subjects include the business owner, employees, and customers of Burger Anata. The involved informant's number five, consisting of the business owner, one employee, and three customers.

Data sources consist of primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained through in-depth interviews with key informants, field observations, and direct interactions with the service system. Secondary data were collected from internal company documents, operational reports, and scientific literature related to Business Model Canvas development. Data analysis in this study was carried out through data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing stages to understand customer needs and satisfaction. The results of this analysis were then used to identify important elements in the Business Model Canvas (BMC), such as value propositions, distribution channels, and customer relationships, to help design more targeted business development strategies.

D. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

The following are the results of the author's analysis of the Anata Burger business model using BMC. The strategies that can be implemented in the nine blocks are described as follows:

Table 1. Initial condition of the Anata BMC Burger

Key Partners	Key Activities	Value Propositions	Customer Relationships	Customer Segments
1. Raw material suppliers	1. Producing Burgers 2. Purchasing Raw Materials	1. Fast service 2. Quality products 3. Relatively low prices	1. Social media interaction 2. Friendly service 3. Special event	1. Age: The primary target can range from children to adults

2. Product packaging	3. Product Promotion	promotions	2. Gender: Targets both men and women
	KEY RESOURCES	CHANNELS	
	1. Human resources for production	1. Offer directly to customers	3. Education: Targets consumers from elementary school to college
	2. Cooking equipment	2. Social media promotion (Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp)	4. All working classes
COST STRUCTURE		REVENUE STREAMS	
1. Raw material costs		1. Main income from selling Anata burgers	
2. Internet costs			
3. Packaging costs			

Table 2. Condition after development of the Anata BMC Burger

KEY PARTNERS	KEY ACTIVITIES	VALUE PROPOSITIONS	CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS
1. Raw material suppliers	1. Producing Anata Burgers	1. Fast service	1. Social media interaction	1. Age: The primary target can range from children to adults
2. Product packaging	2. Purchasing Raw Materials	2. Quality products	2. Friendly service	2. Gender: Targets both men and women
	3. Product Promotion	3. Relatively low prices	3. Special event promotions	3. Education: Targets consumers from elementary school to college
	KEY RESOURCES		CHANNELS	4. All working classes
	1. Human resources for production		1. Offer directly to customers	
	2. Cooking equipment		2. Social media promotion (Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp)	
			3. GoFood	
			4. Digital Payments	
COST STRUCTURE		REVENUE STREAMS		
1. Raw material costs		1. Main income from selling Anata burgers		
2. Internet costs				
3. Packaging costs				

1. Customer Segments

Customer Segment	Burger Anata's main customer segments are children, teenagers, and adults who enjoy savory and delicious snacks.
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Customer Segments refer to the primary groups of customers that a business focuses on. In the context of Burger Anata's business model, the targeted customer segments currently include various age groups, from children who like tasty snacks, teenagers seeking practical and filling food, to adults, especially office workers who often need fast food to accompany their activities. From the interviews conducted, there is a group of customers who regularly make large-quantity purchases.

2. Value Propositions

Value Propositions	Burger Anata offers products at affordable prices while maintaining satisfactory quality for customers, but there are still some obstacles related to impractical packaging.
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Regarding the Value Propositions element, this study found that Burger Anata needs to pursue deeper differentiation in order to compete effectively in the increasingly competitive culinary market. Based on observations and interviews with several sources, the majority of consumers provided feedback indicating that significant development of the product’s value proposition is highly needed.

a) Product Packaging Development (New Appearance)

Product packaging development becomes a primary focus that must be addressed. Consumer feedback reveals that the current burger packaging is still considered impractical.

Figure 3. Before Product Packaging Development

Figure 4. After Product Packaging Development

b) Adding the QRIS Payment Method:

In today's digital era, consumers highly expect fast, easy, and secure payment methods. Therefore, adding the QRIS (Quick Response Code Indonesian Standard) payment method presents a significant opportunity to enhance the value of these products. By using QRIS, consumers can make digital payments without the need to carry cash, making transactions more practical and efficient.

3. Channels

Channels	Burger Anata reaches customers through several channels, such as physical outlets, as well as being active on social media Instagram, WhatsApp.
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Channels are the pathways or methods a company uses to convey product value to customers. Currently, Burger Anata does not market its products through major online sales platforms like GoFood or other similar apps that are popular among fast food consumers.

4. Customer Relationship

Relationship Customers	The relationship built is interactive through feedback from promotional media and fast and responsive handling of customer complaints via the comments and message features on social media Instagram and WhatsApp.
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In an effort to build strong relationships with customers, Burger Anata has implemented various strategies. One approach is offering promotions and discounts through social media at specific times, known as special event promotions.

5. Key Resources

Key Resources	The most important resources for achieving this business goal are skilled labor and quality raw materials. Furthermore, sound planning and routine resource management are also crucial for the business to run smoothly and produce products that satisfy customers.
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In the context of Burger Anata, these primary resources include both human labor and the equipment used in the production process. These two aspects complement each other, supporting smooth daily operations. Burger Anata employees typically perform operational tasks such as food production and direct customer service. The business owner also participates in these activities to ensure daily processes run smoothly. Meanwhile, managerial responsibilities are also vital to business management.

6. Key Partners

Key Resources	Burger Anata has currently collaborated with two strategic partners in the local market: Warung Pajja and Warung Hilda. These two stalls serve as indirect distribution points for Burger Anata products, making their products more accessible to the local community.
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At Burger Anata, our partnerships encompass several key parties, particularly suppliers of raw materials and packaging, which are key components in the production process. These supplier partnerships enable Burger Anata to achieve more competitive prices than the general market.

7. Revenue Streams

Revenue Streams	Burger Anata's revenue comes from direct product sales at outlets and also through online platforms (social media).
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At Burger Anata, the primary source of revenue comes from direct burger sales at physical outlets. Customers can come directly to the store to place an order and enjoy the product. This direct sales method is considered one of the most stable and reliable ways to generate daily revenue for Burger Anata.

8. Key Activities

Key Activities	Key activities include producing quality burgers, managing raw material stocks, and running promotions and sales processes well.
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At Burger Anata, the core activities conducted include several stages, starting with raw material management. This process involves receiving and monitoring the stock of required raw materials to ensure their quality is always maintained before being processed into final products. The raw material processing is carried out carefully to produce ready-to-eat burgers that are not only delicious but also of high quality, thus meeting customer expectations. Based on internal analysis and evaluation, Burger Anata realizes the need to develop these key activities by adding more intensive market research. Market research becomes a strategic step to better understand the latest trends in marketing and the continuously evolving consumer preferences.

9. Cost Structure

Cost Structure	The largest costs in a business usually come from purchasing raw materials used to make products. In addition, there are also additional costs such as other unexpected needs required to ensure daily business operations run smoothly.
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At Burger Anata, cost structure management is divided into two main categories: fixed costs and variable costs. These two categories complement each other and play an important role in maintaining the smoothness and efficiency of business operations. A deep understanding of the cost structure is crucial for Burger Anata in the financial planning and effective budget management process. By knowing the allocation of expenses between fixed and variable costs, management can create more targeted cost control strategies. This also enables Burger Anata to maintain financial stability and minimize the risk of losses due to waste or unplanned expenses.

Tabel 3. Cost structure

Components	Cost (Rp)
Raw Materials & Packaging	54.400.000
Labor costs	18.000.000
Total Cost	72.400.000

Burger Anata has been intensively developing its business using the Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach over the past two months. In this development process, there are several key elements involved. The entire business development process aims to ensure that Burger Anata can adapt to the continuously changing market dynamics while improving productivity and service quality. The implementation of the Business Model Canvas is not only a planning tool but also serves as a practical guide that helps the company make precise and focused decisions.

DISCUSSION

The placement of this research will strengthen the argument that the findings from Burger Anata align with those of other studies. Previous research concluded that the Business Model Canvas (BMC) design for Megah Ria involved elements that were retained, modified, and added. Some of the changes included customer segments, key activities, marketing channels, as well as the addition of new resources and partners. With the implementation of the new business model, Megah Ria is expected to better meet customer needs, increase competitiveness, and adapt to the digital era. Recommendations for the business owner include promptly adopting digital marketing strategies, adding business partners, and optimizing the use of social media to expand market reach (Ilmah et al, 2024).

Research (Vebrianty et al., 2025) emphasizes that business development using the BMC approach is important for maintaining product quality, building customer relationships, and strengthening marketing strategies and partnerships in facing local competition. A study (Farhan Harahap et al., 2024) shows that MSME burger businesses utilizing BMC can formulate strategies to maximize their business potential. (Wicaksono et al., 2017) assert that in BMC-based business development, key resources, key activities, and key partners are the main elements that should be prioritized. Although the study was conducted in the electricity sector, these findings are relevant for culinary MSMEs like Burger Anata, especially in strengthening collaboration with suppliers and optimizing operational activities.

Research on MSME Mojokerto Sayur (MOSAY) found that a growth-oriented business development strategy with improvements in each BMC element increased sales volume. This finding indicates that Burger Anata also needs to conduct continuous evaluation of the nine BMC blocks to support business sustainability and sales growth (Islam & Iyer-Raniga, 2023). This concept can be adopted by Burger Anata not only to survive but also to grow through product innovation and the utilization of digital channels.

This study aims to comprehensively examine how the application of business innovation through the Business Model Canvas (BMC) can support development and enhance Burger Anata’s competitiveness amid increasingly intense competition in

the fast-food market. The main focus is on analyzing market trends and consumer preferences to open up business development opportunities, as well as the influence of BMC implementation in improving business competitiveness.

Through an innovative strategy approach based on BMC, Burger Anata is able to manage the business more structurally and efficiently, thereby improving overall business performance. A comprehensive mapping of the nine BMC elements equips the company to recognize internal potential and adapt to continuously changing market dynamics. This aligns with previous research results showing that focused analysis of elements in the BMC helps small and medium enterprises optimize business strategies systematically (Pascucci et al., 2023).

From the market segmentation perspective, Burger Anata identifies a broad target market ranging from children to adults, showing significant market potential for business development. Previous research also emphasizes the importance of proper market segmentation in supporting increased sales and market penetration (Chandra, 2021). Customers appreciate the quality burger products with friendly service, which is Burger Anata's main value proposition. However, innovation in packaging design and the addition of digital payment methods like QRIS are important aspects that need to be developed to enhance product appeal in line with modern market trends (Djaddang, 2024).

Developing more practical and eco-friendly packaging by using food-grade paper to replace plastic packaging adds value for consumers and strengthens brand image. This is in line with studies showing that innovative packaging can increase purchase intention and consumer satisfaction (Muliansyah et al., 2022). The digital payment method QRIS provides convenience and ease, increasing transaction efficiency and supporting sales growth, while strengthening Burger Anata's competitive position in the digital era (Gabriella & Yuldinawati, 2025).

Regarding human resource (HR) management, this study finds that a clearer division of roles and more structured HR management are needed to improve operational effectiveness and optimal service. This is supported by previous studies emphasizing the importance of employee competence and professionalism in delivering excellent service that enhances customer loyalty (Puspitasari et al., 2023). Clear role allocation among production, management, and marketing is an urgent need for business sustainability.

Strategic partnerships with raw material suppliers and delivery service providers are crucial factors in maintaining smooth operations and reducing business risks. Collaborations with supplier partners allow Burger Anata to obtain competitive prices, especially for bulk purchases, thereby encouraging business efficiency. Additionally, partnerships with online motorcycle taxi applications offer practical and effective distribution solutions (Chandra, 2021).

Burger Anata's main revenue stream comes from burger sales with a significant contribution, while income from side dishes is smaller. A revenue diversification approach through digital channels and special promotions is considered important to add variety to revenue streams and improve financial stability, as recommended by previous research (Yu, 2025).

Overall, the implementation of the Business Model Canvas creates a holistic and integrative business development, driving business growth through product innovation, digital marketing, and responsive service. This approach also supports fast and precise strategic decision-making to enhance competitiveness in a dynamic culinary market. A comprehensive understanding of the BMC elements allows Burger Anata to design data-driven strategies based on current market and customer needs, enabling it to sustain and develop its position continuously (Osterwalder et al., 2019)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results, the study shows that the implementation of the Business Model Canvas (BMC) plays a crucial role in the business development of Burger Anata. By mapping the nine main components of the BMC, the business owner can gain a comprehensive understanding of the business structure. This helps in designing more targeted strategies to increase sales and strengthen competitiveness in the market. The research concludes that analyzing market trends and consumer preferences is an important foundation for identifying business development opportunities for Burger Anata. Understanding consumer needs and tastes, including direct feedback from customers, can guide the business to innovate products and services that better meet market expectations. Furthermore, the implementation of the Business Model Canvas (BMC) has proven effective in enhancing Burger Anata's competitiveness. Through evaluating the nine main BMC elements, the business has successfully improved its business strategies structurally, such as modernized packaging innovation, utilization of digital channels, and improved service quality. Thus, the combination of market analysis and BMC implementation makes a tangible contribution to Burger Anata in strengthening

its competitive position, expanding market reach, and increasing business sustainability amid intensifying competition in the culinary industry. Overall, the use of the BMC has shown significant contributions to business progress, evidenced by improvements in various business performance indicators. The thorough mapping of BMC components assists Burger Anata in setting a clear business direction, optimizing internal potential, and strengthening competitiveness in a tight market competition.

Based on the research findings, it is recommended that Burger Anata continue to conduct evaluations and innovations in applying Business Model Canvas (BMC) strategies to remain relevant to changing market trends and to adapt to dynamic business competition.

REFERENCES

1. Akbar, M., Rakib, M., Isma, A., & Sanusi, D. A. (2024). Development of Sustainable Business Models through Internal Partnerships Efforts to Expand Consumer Reach. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 07(03), 1904–1909. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V7-i3-52>
2. Akin, M. S. (2024). Enhancing e-commerce competitiveness: A comprehensive analysis of customer experiences and strategies in the Turkish market. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 10(1), 100222. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2024.100222>
3. Chandra, G. A. (2021). Steak. *An A-Z of Food and Drink*, 76–85. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acref/9780192803511.013.1200>
4. Djaddang, S. (2024). Literature Review Study: Factors That Influence Customer Satisfaction-Muphimin et.al Literature Review Study: Factors That Influence Customer Satisfaction. *Jurnal Ekonomi*, 13(03), 2024. <https://doi.org/10.54209/ekonomi.v13i03>
5. Farhan Harahap, M., Nawawi, Z. M., & Syahbudi, M. (2024). SWOT Analysis of Sikeling Burger Business Development Strategy Using the Business Model Canvas Approach. *Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia (JESI) ISSN*, 14(1), 47–58. <https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.3124.3483>
6. Gabriella, D., & Yuldinawati, L. (2025). the Use of E-Commerce and Qris As Digital Payment Solutions To Enhance Sales Performance in Msmes in West Java. *Indonesian Interdisciplinary Journal of Sharia Economics (IJSE)*, 8(1), 1157–1178.
7. Handoyo, S., Suharman, H., Ghani, E. K., & Soedarsono, S. (2023). A business strategy, operational efficiency, ownership structure, and manufacturing performance: The moderating role of market uncertainty and competition intensity and its implication on open innovation. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 9(2), 100039. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2023.100039>
8. Ilmah, P.A, Rakib, M, A. S. (2024). Business Model Design in Developing Small Businesses: A Business Model Canvas Approach. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(8), 1700–1715. <https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2024.8080124>
9. Islam, M. T., & Iyer-Raniga, U. (2023). Circular Business Model Value Dimension Canvas: Tool Redesign for Innovation and Validation through an Australian Case Study. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(15). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151511553>
10. Lestari, L. I., Rakib, M., Asmayanti, A., & Sanusi, D. A. (2024). Star-Up Business Development in an Effort to Increase Competitiveness: A Development Research. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 07(06), 3869–3878. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/v7-i6-37>
11. Li, H., Sajjad, N., Wang, Q., Ali, A. M., Khaqan, Z., & Amina, S. (2019). Influence of transformational leadership on employees' innovative work behavior in sustainable organizations: Test of mediation and moderation processes. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(6), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11061594>
12. Malik, I. (2020). Strategi Perencanaan Dan Pengembangan Bisnis Dalam Menghadapi Perdagangan Bebas Masyarakat Ekonomi Asean. *Negotium: Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 3(1), 39. <https://doi.org/10.29103/njiab.v3i1.3051>
13. Nursini, N. (2020). Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) and poverty reduction: empirical evidence from Indonesia. *Development Studies Research*, 7(1), 153–166. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21665095.2020.1823238>
14. Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y., Smith, A., & Movement, T. (2019). *You're holding a handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers striving to defy outmoded business models and design tomorrow's enterprises. It's a book for the . . . written by.*

15. Pascucci, F., Savelli, E., & Gistri, G. (2023). How digital technologies reshape marketing: evidence from a qualitative investigation. *Italian Journal of Marketing*, 2023(1), 27–58. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43039-023-00063-6>
16. Puspitasari, I., Rusydi, F., Nuzulita, N., & Hsiao, C.-S. (2023). Investigating the role of utilitarian and hedonic goals in characterizing customer loyalty in E-marketplaces. *Heliyon*, 9(8), e19193. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e19193>
17. Putera, W., Rakib, M., & Sahabuddin, R. (2021). Competitive Advantages Influence on Marketing Performance: Study on Food and Beverage MSMEs. *THE American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (THE AJHSSR)*, 04(01), 75–83. www.theajhssr.com
18. Rahmi, Rakib, M., Anugrah Sanusi, D., & Isma, A. (2024). Business Model Design Using the Business Model Canvas Approach: Case Study of the “Fishbon” Fish Floss Business. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management (IJAEM)*, 6(06), 625–632. <https://doi.org/10.35629/5252-0606625632>
19. Rakib, M., Azis, M., Najib, M., & Isma, A. (2024). Impact of Digital Literacy, Business Innovation, Competitive Advantage on the Existence of SMEs: A quantitative study in Makassar City, Indonesia. *Quality - Access to Success*, 25(198), 277–283. <https://doi.org/10.47750/QAS/25.198.30>
20. Surya, B., Menne, F., Sabhan, H., Suriani, S., Abubakar, H., & Idris, M. (2021). Economic Growth, Increasing Productivity of SMEs, and Open Innovation. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 7(1), 20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc7010020>
21. Vebrianty, V. F., Rahmah, Z. F., & Sarnando, G. P. (2025). *Development Of Mochi Daifuku Business Using Business Model Canvas (Bmc) Method In Bekasi Regency*. 4(02), 154–162.
22. Wicaksono, A. A., Syarief, R., & Suparno, O. (2017). Business Model in Electricity Industry Using Business Model Canvas Approach; the Case of Pt. Xyz. *Indonesian Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship*, 3(1), 52–63. <https://doi.org/10.17358/ijbe.3.1.52>
23. Yu, X. (2025). How Does Revenue Diversification Affect the Financial Health of Sustainable Entrepreneurship Organizations in China ? A Fuzzy Set Qualitative Comparative Analysis. *Sustainability*, 17(4377), 5–7.

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